

DEVELOPMENT OF PACKER MOUNTING IN REPAIR WELLS

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Abstract

Packers are downhole equipment that is essential equipment in well workover operations to protect the production string from reservoir pressure.

The sleeve assembly, which is the main assembly of the packer, requires that during setting the packer is not damaged and does not stick to the inside of the well when running into the well, and that the packer is set correctly. When mounting the packer in the well, it is necessary to ensure full balance.

To ensure balance when setting the packer, in workover wells, care must be taken to ensure that the packer is lowered into the well at low speed. When lowering the packer into the well, it is also necessary to control the descent speed and know the pattern of change in the dependence of the dynamic force on the descent speed. The calculation of the allowable compressive load on the packer equipment used in well repair is considered. A stability criterion is proposed that takes into account bending stresses that occur when a packer is mounted in a well.

Depending on the diameter of the tubing, the critical value of the compressive force acting on the packer was determined, and a new expression was obtained for calculating the allowable load acting on the packer used in the repair well. The critical compression force was calculated depending on the diameter of the well pipes.

Depending on the diameter of the tubing, the numerical values of the critical force on the packer were determined. It was found that the value of bending stresses as a criterion for static stability corresponds to 15 % of the yield strength when the packer is mounted in a repair well.

When mounting the packer in repair wells, care must be taken to ensure that the packer is lowered into the well at low speed to ensure balance.

Keywords: packer setting, compressive load, balanced fit, workover wells, downhole equipment.

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1. Introduction

Packers are downhole equipment that is essential equipment in well workover operations to protect the production string from reservoir pressure.

Packers are used in the oil industry to isolate the space between the tubing and the production pipe (annular space) during the operation of various wells in underground structures. Also, packers are used to eliminate the impact on the formation of underlying gas-liquid systems [1].

The sealing assembly of the existing packer design consists of a sealing collar, packer barrel, cylinder, piston, body, spring and O-ring [1].

The main disadvantage of this design is that during operation at a critical pressure value or in any other case, additional forces act on the seal cuff. When the pressure changes, this rubber

sealing cuff cyclically (periodically) oscillates. The fact that this oscillatory movement continues for a long time, and the deformation of the sealing collar exceeds the allowable limit, causes structural fatigue. As a result of these fatigues, minimal cracks are formed, which also turn into maximum cracks. Also, due to the additional compressive force, the sealing collar is compressed, resulting in deformation of the edges due to the expansion of its volume. This leads to an overload of the structure, since it is impossible to deform the edges in the slot where the collar sits, resulting in the destruction of the sealing collar. If the packer is incorrectly seated, its collars will be subjected to non-parallel loading, which will lead to uneven stresses in the internal sections. As a result, the packer sleeves fail. This leads to the fact that the packer quickly fails and loses its efficiency. To get rid of this problem, it is necessary to ensure the correct mounting of the packer in the well.

The sleeve assembly, which is the main assembly of the packer, requires that the packer is not damaged when running into the well, does not adhere to the interior of the well, and is set correctly. When mounting the packer in the well, it is necessary to ensure full balance.

When mounting the packer in repair wells, care must be taken to ensure that the packer is lowered into the well at low speed to ensure balance. It is necessary to control the rate of descent when running the packer into the well and to know the pattern of change in the dependence of the dynamic force on the rate of descent.

Various studies have been carried out in this area. The closest research work to our research is the development of a mathematical model that determines the contact pressure, taking into account the geometric characteristics of the collar and the physical properties of the material during self-tightening of the packer collar. In this case, it provides a determination of the contact pressures that occur in the collar after the packer is seated in the well. It is possible to theoretically determine the critical force that causes the initial contact pressure when the packer is in the hole. It is impossible to determine the experimental study of this issue in the laboratory.

Therefore, it is necessary to reduce the dynamic impact of the packer in the well and it is required to determine the contact pressure that causes self-sealing of its cuffs under these conditions.

Considering the foregoing, in research works the critical force that occurs when packing a packer in a well is determined, subject to reduction.

2. Materials and methods of research

In this research work, measures were considered to mitigate the dynamic effect [1–3] of the applied force, depending on the principle of setting the packer (**Fig. 1**). Packers are driven mechanically, that is, force is applied to the packer mechanically (mechanical packers), hydro-mechanically (both mechanical and hydraulic packers), and hydraulically (applied to hydraulic packers mechanically or hydraulically). The load created during the setting of the packer causes stress deformation of the rubber cuffs. Therefore, the selected material of the cuffs must correspond to the load. This load is applied to the packer seals not in a static, but in a dynamic state [3–5]. To suppress the impact of the load, it is necessary to achieve a «balanced mounting» of the packer in the well – this is the descent of the packer into the well, the mounting of its seals in the casing, the removal (release) of the packer from the well [6–9]. Consequently:

$$Y_{w.s.} = Y_w + \frac{\Delta P_{pack}}{h_{pack}}, \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{w.s.}$ – specific gravity of the washing solution, N/m²; Y_w – the specific gravity of water, N/m²; ΔP_{pack} – the pressure drop across the packer, MPa; h_{pack} – the depth of the packer mounting in the well, m.

To provide the necessary axial load for shallow wells, let's determine the number of tubing to which the packer is attached. Sometimes, instead of tubing, drill pipes (200–300 m long) are used, inside which flushing solution is filled, and water is brought to the surface:

$$H\gamma_{w.s.} = \Delta P_{pack} + h_{w.s.}\gamma_{w.s.} + (H_{pack} - h_{w.s.})\gamma_w, \quad (2)$$

where

$$h_{w.s} = H_{pack} - \frac{\Delta P_{pack}}{\gamma_{w.s} - \gamma_w}. \quad (3)$$

Therefore, in repair wells, part of the packer pipes, defined by expression (3), must be filled with flushing solution (the rest – with water), which (2) is a condition for fulfilling the balanced landing criterion.

Fig. 1. Well packer

When the packer is supported on the casing string, it limits mixing of the tubing by causing buckling and twisting as it compresses the cross section of the tubing.

Since bending is considered in a plane, the calculation of the critical compressive load for packer pipes using the Euler formula [9–11] gives an approximate result. Another measurement criterion should be sought – the «stability criterion», and the «spatial bend» having a real condition should be considered.

Let's write the equation of the axis of the «helix» line for packer pipes (also for the «liner»):

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (R_{well} - R_{p.p.}) \cos t, \\ y &= (R_{well} - R_{p.p.}) \sin t, \\ z &= b \cdot t, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

here R_{well} – the radius of the well; $R_{p.p.}$ – the radius of the packer pipes (together with the liner); t – the angle of torsion; $b = s/2\pi$ characterizes the pitch of the helix s . If the length of one pipe screw is l_{cr} , then:

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{l_{cr}^2}{4\pi^2} - (R_{well} - R_{p.p.})^2}. \quad (5)$$

Then the radius of curvature of the helical spiral can be determined as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{(R_{well} - R_{p.p.})^2 + b^2}{R_{well} - R_{p.p.}} - \frac{l_{cr}^2}{4\pi^2 (R_{well} - R_{p.p.})}. \quad (6)$$

For a given radius of curvature, if to mark the compression load of the packer pipes as – G , and the cross-sectional area – F , then the bending stress corresponding to this radius of curvature can be determined as the sum:

$$\sigma = \sigma_{cr} + \sigma_b = \frac{G}{F} + \frac{FJ}{\rho W}, \quad (7)$$

where J and W are the moments of inertia and resistance of the cross section of pipes during bending.

It should be noted that in expression (1) torsion stresses must be added to the compressive and bending stresses, but the evaluation showed that, compared with other stresses, the torsion stresses are of very small importance. Thus, the «basic criterion of durability» of packer pipes can be written as follows:

$$\frac{G}{F} + \frac{EJ}{\rho W} \leq \sigma_y, \quad (8)$$

where σ_y – the yield strength of the pipe material. Therefore, from expression (8) it is possible to determine the allowable compressive load on the packer pipes (as well as on the liner):

$$G_{cr.} = F \left(\sigma_y - \frac{EJ}{\rho W} \right), \quad (9)$$

or taking into account (8), one can write:

$$J_{cr} = 1.98 \sqrt[3]{\frac{EJ}{q}},$$

$$G_{cr} = F \left[\sigma_y - 5.04 \left(D_{well} - D_{p.p.} \sqrt[3]{\frac{EJ \cdot q^2}{W}} \right) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$5.04 = 2\pi^2/1.98 - d \cdot r,$$

where the values of the compressive critical allowable force generated in the packer pipes obtained in (10) are given in **Table 1**.

Table 1 shows that the results obtained can be used as a criterion for static stability, since bending stresses sometimes reach 15 % of the yield strength value:

$$\sigma_t = E\alpha(T_1 - T_0), \quad (11)$$

where E – modulus of elasticity of steel; $E = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa; α – coefficient of linear expansion; $\alpha = 11 \cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/degree; T_0 – the initial temperature; T_1 – the final temperature.

The drop in temperature also has a negative effect on the elastic modulus of the material (**Fig. 2**). As can be seen from **Fig. 2** when the elastic modulus E increases with increasing temperature (for example, 300 °C). The analysis shows that the tensile strength (σ_t) and the yield strength (σ_y) of the pipe decrease as the elastic modulus characteristic (E) decreases.

In wells, it often fluctuates between 100–250 °C, then it can be written that the elastic modulus E , with an error of 1 %, changes linearly with the temperature drop:

$$E_t = E_0 - K_t^E \cdot \Delta T, \quad (12)$$

where ΔT – the temperature drop (depending on the modulus of elasticity); E_t , E_0 – the moduli of elasticity at temperature T and 20 °C, respectively; K_t^E – coefficient of change in the modulus of elasticity with temperature, the average value for metals $K_t^E = 70$ MPa/°C per °C.

Table 1
Values of compressive critical allowable force

Sample No.	Pipe diameter, mm	Wall thickness, mm	Compressive critical force (kN) in hole diameters (mm)				
1	60	5	330	320	310	50	40
2	73	5	330	850	660	40	70
3	89	5	330	890	630	10	10
4	114	8	330	890	870	50	50
5	114	10	330	890	870	50	170

Fig. 2. Dependence of elasticity on temperature:
1 – according to the 1st sample; 2 – according to the 2nd sample; 3 – according to the 3rd sample;
4 – according to the 4th sample; 5 – according to the 5th sample

When the pipe (liner) begins to bend under its own weight, its critical length can be determined as follows:

$$f_{cr} = \frac{1}{98} \sqrt{\frac{EJ}{q}}$$

For example, if for a normal temperature of 20 °C, $E = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa, then at 170 °C:

$$(E)_{170} = 2.1 \cdot 10^5 - 20 \cdot 150 = 1.995 \cdot 10^5 \text{ MPa i.e., reduced to 5 \%}$$

In the same way, assuming a linear change σ_s of the dependence of the packer pipe yield on the well temperature of 250 °C, it can be written:

$$(\sigma_s)_t = (\sigma_s)_o - K_t^{G_s} \Delta T, \quad (13)$$

where $(\sigma_s)_t$ – the yield strength at temperature – t ; $(\sigma_s)_o$ – also at a normal temperature of 20 °C; ΔT – temperature change (fall); $K_t^{G_s}$ – coefficient of temperature change in fluidity. For alloy steels with a temperature change from 20 °C to 300 °C, the following is obtained:

$$K_t^{G_s} = 47.3 \cdot \frac{\text{N/sn}^2}{\text{°S}} = 47.3 \cdot 10^4 \cdot \frac{\text{N/m}^2}{\text{°S}}$$

Based on the calculations, the obtained value $K_t^{G_s}$ – when mounting the packer, requires the correct choice of the material of the packer pipes, taking into account the temperature criteria of the medium.

3. Results and discussion

With a safe setting of the packer, it is necessary to achieve the cancellation of the impact load and the «balanced fit» of the packer in the well. On the basis of the above formula (1), it can be said that the descent of the packer into the well depends on the moderate mounting of its seals on the string and return to its previous position when it is removed (released) from the well.

The necessary axial load must be ensured in the tubing to which the packer is connected. To do this, the part of the packer pipes that will be used in the workover wells must be filled with flushing solution (2) – to meet the criteria for a balanced mounting.

Due to the limited displacement of the tubing when the packer is supported on the string, compressive stresses, buckling and twisting occur in the cross section of the pipes.

The calculation of the critical compressive load for packer pipes using formula (10) gives an approximate result, since the bend is considered in the plane. In this case, another measurement criterion, the «stability criterion», should be sought, since «spatial curvature», which is a real condition, should be taken into account.

The task posed in the research work was considered in space on the basis of the stability criterion, which is a real condition. An expression has been obtained for calculating the values of the compressive critical allowable force formed in the packer pipes.

$$J_{cr} = \frac{1}{98} \sqrt[3]{\frac{EJ}{q}},$$

$$G_{cr} = F \left[\sigma_y - 5.04 \left(D_{well} - D_{p.p.} \sqrt[3]{\frac{EJ \cdot q^2}{W}} \right) \right], \quad (14)$$

$$5.04 = \frac{2\pi^2}{1.98 - d \cdot r}.$$

The results obtained from expression (14) can be used as a criterion for static stability.

The distribution of the relative pressure created in the packer's sleeve is determined experimentally, ensuring the fit of the packer in the well according to formula (14). **Fig. 3** shows the distribution of stresses on the surface (solid curve 1) and in the middle (solid curve 2) $H/R = 0.25$ depending on the height of the sealant and its radius.

Fig. 3. Relative pressure distribution

From **Fig. 2** it can be seen that as a result of taking into account the critical force, the distribution of the relative pressure created in the packer-seal increases in uniform conditions. No sudden growth or change. This indicates a gradual change in pressure, and this change is already causing self-consolidation.

Proper mounting of a packer in a well is important for many reasons. Ensuring safe operation of the first well. Increase in the productivity of the second well. Protection of the well from damage during mounting and removal of the third packer.

To avoid these problems, the packer must be correctly mounted in the well. When mounting the packer in the well, its collars should not deform more than 20 % of the body. Our proposals will help increase the life of the packer, preventing the above problems.

4. Conclusions

Depending on the diameter of the tubing, the critical value of the compressive force acting on the packer was determined, and a new expression was obtained for calculating the allowable load acting on the packer used in the repair well.

Depending on the diameter of the tubing, the numerical values of the critical force on the packer were determined. It was found that the value of bending stresses as a criterion for static stability corresponds to 15 % of the yield strength when the packer is mounted in a repair well.

It was found that the complete deformation of the seal during the mounting of the packer depends on the value of the compressive force. When choosing the design parameters of the seal, taking into account the critical force of the compressive force ensures an orderly and uniform increase in relative pressure. This increase will ensure the self-sealing of the cuff.

During the experiment, it was found that the deformation of the packer clamps should be equal to 1/5 of its height when the packer is set in order to maintain the magnitude of the bending stress.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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